

Mapping the Open Science Landscape: A Community Dashboard Approach Using the ASAPbio Directory

Isabelle Dorsch*, Marc-André Simard**, Abdelghani Maddi*

* isabelle.dorsch@cnrs.fr; abdelghani.maddi@cnrs.fr
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7391-5189>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9268-8022>
Groupe d'Étude des Méthodes de l'Analyse Sociologique de la Sorbonne, GEMASS,
Sorbonne Université, CNRS, F-75017 Paris, France

** marc-andre.simard.1@umontreal.ca
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3795-0053>
École de bibliothéconomie et des sciences de l'information, Université de Montréal, Montréal, QC, Canada

The rapid emergence of open science (OS) policies and transparency mandates has created a growing need for robust monitoring tools capable of capturing the diversity and dynamics of OS initiatives. Here, we present an interactive community dashboard developed using R Shiny, designed to map and classify global OS initiatives based on data from ASAPbio's prototype directory. Leveraging Multiple Correspondence Analysis and Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components, the dashboard organizes initiatives according to dimensions such as governance models, open source availability, and geographical distribution. This dynamic and customizable tool enables stakeholders to explore the evolving landscape of OS and to identify patterns and gaps across initiatives. Facilitating both expert oversight and community-driven contributions, the dashboard lays the groundwork for a scalable and inclusive observatory of OS practices. Our approach offers a novel framework for tracking the implementation and transformation of OS on a global scale.

1. Introduction

Efforts to monitor open science (OS) have gained momentum in recent years, particularly with the proliferation of open access (OA) mandates from funders and the growing demand for greater transparency in research. Various actors have begun to formalize monitoring frameworks. For example, a Delphi study led to the identification of 19 core OS practices to guide institutional dashboard development in the biomedical field (Cobey et al., 2023). In parallel, national-level efforts such as the French OA monitoring initiative (Bracco et al., 2022; Jeangirard, 2019) have laid the groundwork for large-scale dashboards aimed at tracking compliance and implementation of OA policies. These initiatives reflect the increasing pressure on institutions and researchers to meet the requirements set by funding agencies, some of which — like the NIH and Wellcome Trust — have implemented conditionalities tied to OA compliance (Larivière & Sugimoto, 2018). However, the effectiveness of these measures remains difficult to assess, and compliance varies across disciplines and national contexts (Maddi, 2020; Simard et al., 2022).

Beyond technical infrastructures and compliance tracking, discussions around OS monitoring also raise important questions of scope and representation. As Salamoura and Tsakonas (2024) pointed out, the comprehensiveness and utility of dashboards depend not only on their technical features — such as update frequency, data granularity, and types of access tracked — but also on how information is contextualized and visualized. Moreover, UNESCO (2023) reminds us that OS practices and their monitoring vary widely across regions, depending on local priorities and existing capacities. One often-overlooked dimension is the role of citizen science, which, although marginal in traditional OA dashboards, has shown significant potential in contributing to global agendas such as the Sustainable Development Goals (Fraisl et al., 2020).

1.1 State of Research

For the establishment of an effective OS research infrastructure and to understand the development of OS policies and frameworks, it is not only important to understand the actions and instruments implemented by research councils (Lasthiotakis et al., 2015), but rather by the entire body of OS contributors. UNESCO specifies the importance of adequate OS monitoring, to ensure and to capture the entire transformation from OS and its impacts (UNESCO, 2021, 2023).

In order to contribute to the common understanding of OS and the development of an OS monitoring framework, the Open Science Monitoring Initiative (OSMI) was established by the Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, Inria, PLOS, SPARC Europe, UNESCO, and the Université de Lorraine (Open Science Monitoring Initiative, 2023). OSMI addresses the particle implementation and adoption of OS monitoring principles by bringing together institutions and individuals involved in OS monitoring. They recently set up a first version of principles for OS monitoring (Open Science Monitoring Initiative, 2024). The OSMI principles aim to support the global monitoring of the transition to OS by recognizing diverse approaches, promoting comparability and reuse, and guiding stakeholders in developing their own monitoring tools to assess impacts on research and society.

For monitoring OS, the extent of OA to scientific publications is the most common metric utilised (UNESCO, 2023). This is certainly also due to the long history of OA developments and the implementation of infrastructures (Gong, 2022; Pinfield et al., 2021; Tennant et al., 2016) and the prominent share of OS policies for making research outputs publicly accessible (Chtena et al., 2023). Several OA dashboards on the macro-, meso-, or micro-level emerged, as they constitute a useful tool to visualize data and to monitor progress over time. A comprehensive collection of major dashboards mostly focusing on OA is provided by OSMI (Open Science Monitoring Initiative, 2025). A communality of all these dashboards is their scope on research outputs. An analysis of monitoring systems in Europe reveals that most of them focus on journal publications, while only a few also include information on books or conference proceedings (Salamoura & Tsakonas, 2024).

Monitoring only quantifiable OS outputs and practices potentially distracts from capturing the entire transformation to OS and its impacts. While the adoption of OS is increasing, existing OS monitoring approaches are not sufficient yet to capture all stages of the scientific cycle and across all aspects. To date, no global monitoring framework exists (UNESCO, 2023). It is therefore suggested by Rafols et al. (2024) that the scope of monitoring be broadened to outputs, processes, outcomes, and final impacts, as well as their overall synergy effects. This not only extends the scope of monitoring but also allows for analysing whether the evolution of the research system leads in the desired direction. With only knowledge of the desired outputs, it is not possible to make accurate statements about desired outcomes and impacts associated with them, as therefore there is no data available. Every statement on the effect of the outputs would remain an assumption or hypothesis. OS is likely not the only factor that influences development. Impacts are multifactorial, and other more significant factors may have adverse effects. Likewise, complementary policies may be taken into account (Rafols et al., 2024).

1.2 Research Aim

As demonstrated, initiatives for tracking OA outputs flourish and contribute to the foundation of OS monitoring. However, it is important not to stop at this point and to closely follow their trajectories and consequences (Rafols et al., 2024). We want to add on this by investigating the

interplay of OA initiatives as part of the OPENIT project¹. The OPENIT project seeks to analyze the multifaceted dynamics of the scientific publishing market and “unravel” the complex interdependencies among its various stakeholders. One of our main project goals is to map existing OA efforts, assess their interactions, identify overlaps or synergies, and to highlight their impact on the transformation of the publishing market.

Our overall aim is to provide an initiatives community dashboard for a near real-time classification to enable an overview and comparison for the initiatives similarities and differences. In order to create such a dashboard, we implement a case study on open scholarly communication initiatives based on data from ASAPbio’s prototype directory (Corker & Shaw, 2024). The introduced OS initiatives dashboard serves as a prototype and an open invitation for feedback from the STI community, with the underlying dataset to be refined and further developed based on insights from the OPENIT project.

A dashboard has the advantage of a clear visualisation of selected key figures and factors and further enriches data list collections. In compliance with OS principles, the proposed dashboard gives the opportunity to be accessible for anyone. In addition, everyone has the opportunity to contribute to it through the suggestion of missing or new initiatives. Using a dashboard for analysing OS initiatives in this way is a novel approach, since, to our knowledge, there does not exist such a dashboard yet.

This paper describes the development of the first version of the dashboard by means of ASAPbio’s prototype directory data (Corker & Shaw, 2024) as a case study. Our focus lies on the dashboard development, applied methodology for the data aggregation and analysis, and community feedback. We further provide an outlook of the dashboard development and its data collection of initiatives.

2. Methods

As a part of our effort to map and classify OS initiatives, we have developed an interactive dashboard (<https://amcm.shinyapps.io/openit/>) designed to meet the growing demand for transparency, clarity, and reproducibility in data reporting. As Salamoura and Tsakonas (2024, p. 2) emphasized, “reporting norms require that their operation is simple, iterative and as automated and illustrative as possible.” In line with this approach, our dashboard was built to provide an intuitive interface that enables users to explore OS initiatives across multiple dimensions. It features interactive visualizations, customizable filters, and automated data updates from open sources, making it both user-friendly and methodologically robust.

2.1 Dashboard Creation

The dashboard was created using the R Shiny (<https://shiny.posit.co/>) framework, providing an accessible and engaging platform for users to explore the dataset dynamically.

The R Shiny framework was chosen for its flexibility and interactivity, allowing users to filter and visualize data in real time. The dashboard displays information about categorized initiatives from ASAPbio’s prototype directory (Corker & Shaw, 2024), categorizing them based on key characteristics such as open source availability, governance model, and geographical location. The dashboard also includes a map and calculates interactive plots to allow users to explore relationships between initiatives more intuitively.

The dashboard’s development process involved the following five key steps:

¹Project website project OPENIT: <https://www.gemass.fr/contract/openit/>

1. **Data Integration:** We enriched the ASAPbio dataset by adding geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), ISO3 country codes (<https://www.iban.com/country-codes>), and categorizing initiatives into six thematic categories:
 - Community and Education
 - Data and Infrastructure
 - Journals and Publication Models
 - Open Science and Policies
 - Preprints and Repositories
 - Tools and Research Services

The classification into six thematic categories emerged from an initial Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components (HCPC) (Murtagh & Contreras, 2012), which helped reveal underlying structures in the dataset. These categories were then further refined and validated through the authors' expertise in the field.

2. **Interactive Visualizations:** To facilitate the exploration of the data, Leaflet (<https://leafletjs.com/index.html>) was used to create an interactive map that displays initiatives geographically. Additionally, Plotly (<https://plotly.com/r/>) was employed to generate interactive charts, enabling users to visualize the distribution of initiatives across different categories, governance models, and geographic locations.
3. **Long Term Hosting and Maintenance, User Contribution, and Rights Management:** At the moment, the dashboard is hosted on a long-term R Shiny server. On the main page of the dashboard (see Figure 1), users can access two clickable buttons—one leading to a Google Form where new initiatives can be proposed, and another linking to the dataset used for the visualizations and analysis. At this stage, only users with editing rights can modify the dataset directly. However, we plan to gradually extend editing access to other trusted collaborators working on similar efforts, such as those involved in the OSMI initiative (<https://open-science-monitoring.org/>), in order to foster broader community engagement while maintaining data quality and oversight.
4. **Code Availability:** The code used to create the dashboard and handle data processing is available on GitHub, ensuring the methodology is reproducible. You can access the code at <https://github.com/abdelghani-maddi/osinit/blob/main/app.R>.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the dashboard's landing page (April 2025).

2.2 Statistical Methods of Classification and Clustering

We used Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) (Holzinger & Harman, 1941; Kline, 2014) to examine the relationships between categorical variables, namely: the governance model (community-driven or not), profit orientation (for-profit vs. not-for-profit), and the Category. MCA helped reduce the dimensionality of the dataset based on all characteristics simultaneously, rather than relying on a single categorical label. It makes it easier to identify patterns and relationships, while preserving the categorical structure.

To further analyze these relationships, we applied HCPC (Murtagh & Contreras, 2012), which grouped initiatives based on the MCA results. HCPC was particularly useful for visualizing the clustering of initiatives and identifying patterns in how initiatives relate to each other based on their characteristics.

The combination of MCA and HCPC allowed us to visualize the relationships between initiatives and interpret these relationships more effectively. The methods were implemented in R, using key packages such as FactoMineR for MCA (Lê et al., 2008) and Factoextra for HCPC (Kassambara & Mundt, 2016). These statistical techniques provided a clear framework for interpreting the large and complex dataset, revealing patterns and clusters that might not have been immediately apparent.

3. Results

In this section, we present the results of the MCA, followed by a HCPC, to identify patterns and groupings among OS initiatives.

3.1 MCA results

The MCA visualization maps OS initiatives in a biplot (a two-dimensional space) based on shared characteristics (community governance, focus, open source, etc.). The further away initiatives are, the more they differ. The first axis, explaining 26.75% of the inertia, highlights the main differentiation between organizations, while the second axis, at 14.55%, brings the total variance to over 41%. This is a reasonable level for categorical data but indicates some complexity remains.

Key patterns emerge from the plot. Axis 1 distinguishes between the Preprints and Repositories category (orange) on the left, and the Tools and Research Services category (green) on the right, reflecting a divide between archival infrastructures and technology-driven service platforms. Preprints like arXiv and Zenodo are nonprofit, community-driven, and foundational to OS. Tools such as protocols.io and scite.ai tend to have hybrid or commercial models. Axis 2 adds a further layer of differentiation, with the Open Science and Policies cluster (purple) isolated from any other initiative in the upper-left quadrant. Initiatives like SPARC focus more on advocacy and policy, setting them apart from infrastructure or publishing tools.

The Community and Education category (blue) is more dispersed, suggesting internal differences in governance and organizational models across education-related initiatives. Journals and publication platforms (red), like PeerJ and F1000, are clustered in the bottom-right quadrant, often alongside tools, implying hybrid models where journals integrate additional services. Finally, Data and Infrastructure initiatives (brown) are centered, indicating their connective role within the ecosystem.

suggests a strong structural alignment around data accessibility, publication hosting, and open metadata services.

Figure 3. Results from HCPC (n = 96 initiatives).

The green cluster groups initiatives focused on research evaluation, publishing innovations, and community engagement. It includes journals and platforms like PLOS, eLife, PeerJ, and ASAPbio, as well as initiatives such as MetaDocencia and Peer Community In. These actors are characterized by their efforts to reform peer review, promote early-stage research sharing, and strengthen educational or community-based models of scholarly communication. Their proximity in the clustering indicates shared commitments to openness in both dissemination and governance practices.

The red cluster includes platforms such as Scite.ai, Altmetric, and Dimensions — tools that offer alternative and enriched metrics for assessing research impact. These services go beyond traditional citation counts, emphasizing real-time engagement, media attention, and broader societal influence. Their grouping highlights a distinct functional role in the OS ecosystem, centered on evaluation and visibility.

A smaller turquoise cluster gathers advocacy and policy-oriented initiatives such as Open Science MOOC, OASPA, and Open Access Button. These organizations focus on shaping policy environments, promoting best practices, and supporting systemic transition to openness across the research landscape. Their alignment suggests a shared institutional mission of norm-setting and advocacy for structural change.

This data-driven classification—based on MCA and hierarchical clustering—goes beyond predefined categories to reveal latent similarities in how these initiatives operate and organize themselves. It provides a more nuanced understanding of the OS ecosystem, helping to identify synergies and potential collaborations among actors with overlapping missions and complementary services.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Using ASAPbio's prototype directory (Corker & Shaw, 2024) as a starting point, we developed a dashboard for near real-time classification of OS initiatives for community feedback and co-development. The results of this case study as a work-in-progress highlight first information on the interplay of the initiatives through the use of MCA and HCPC. The MCA followed by hierarchical clustering revealed that variables such as governance model, non-profit status, and functional attributes structure the diversity of OS initiatives. Rather than confirming the initial six typological categories, the statistical classification highlights four main clusters based on shared operational and organizational characteristics (Figure 3).

This conference paper represents an opportunity to bring up a series of topics that need to be addressed before the next steps of the project:

- 1) Community involvement: how do we design community participation for the development and the management of the initiative? What steps are needed in order to ensure data quality? Are moderators to approve submissions and data quality needed?
- 2) Scope of the project: how do we define inclusion and exclusion criteria? For instance, the inclusion of repositories would replicate work done by various initiatives such as OpenDOAR² and the ROAR³.
- 3) Real-time updating and data sharing: how often should the dashboard be automatically updated (currently, every 10 minutes)? Should the data, similarly to the code, be accessible and shared in real time? Research shows that vague legal requirements for data sharing may prevent researchers from reusing data (Salamoura & Tsakonas, 2024, p. 6).
- 4) Dashboard features and aesthetic: what features are needed to improve the usability of the dashboard? Which features further enhance the degree of information? How can we make it most useful for the community?

Following the monitoring recommendation of UNESCO (2021), we aim for the dashboard to be as open as possible with the methodology, data and code being available to all for maximum reproducibility and reuse. Based on the questions we raise above, the community-based approach could include the management and updating of the dashboard by the OS community by using the "Add initiatives and enrich data" button, so that any member of the community will be able to submit new initiatives and suggest changes. Once approved by moderators chosen by the community, the dashboard automatically updates in real time.

As previously mentioned, much of previous and ongoing OS and OA monitoring activities have been centered around quantitative data such as policy compliance, spendings, the uptake of OA, data sharing, etc. Thus and in the context of the OPENIT project, we want to focus future developments of the dashboard on the synergies between OA initiatives to build on the knowledge of OA outcomes as indicated in 1.1. Extending the scope of monitoring practices also goes in line to prevent a streetlight effect (Davies et al., 2021), where the spotlight focuses on the narrower or more straightforward, and easy to measure aspects (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021); like only OS outputs such as the number of OA publications in the case for monitoring OS-related aspects (Rafols et al., 2024). Such an extension should also rely on qualitative approaches. In particular, invisible practices could be analyzed via direct inquiries, surveys, qualitative approaches, (Rafols et al., 2024) and the inclusion of case studies for capturing diversity (Bezuidenhout et al., 2024) to analyse their impact on OS.

² <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

³ <https://roar.eprints.org/>

OA can be granted to research publications, research data, metadata, open educational resources, software, source code, and hardware and is summarized as open scientific knowledge by UNESCO (2021). Our future work will, therefore, also include refining inclusion and exclusion criteria for the dashboard. Thereby, our scope will lay on OA initiatives, in alignment with the OPENIT project. However, that does not necessarily limit the dashboard to OA. Ideally, the dashboard can provide a base for capturing synergies within the entire OS landscape with the help of the community.

Despite growing institutional and policy commitments to OS, efforts to monitor its implementation remain fragmented, uneven, and often blind to the diversity of grassroots initiatives. Our prototype dashboard offers a concrete step toward bridging that gap — not by claiming exhaustiveness, but by making visible the contours of an ecosystem too often viewed through the narrow lens of OA publishing. In doing so, it invites the community to rethink what it means to “track progress” in OS: not as a top-down compliance exercise, but as a shared, evolving responsibility grounded in transparency and inclusion.

Finally, one potential limitation of our approach is its dependency on community acceptance. To mitigate this, we intend to engage the community at an early stage of the development process, ensuring their perspectives are integrated from the outset.

Open science practices

The enriched dataset, along with the results of the clustering analysis, is directly accessible through the interactive dashboard available at <https://amcm.shinyapps.io/openit/>. The source code used to develop the dashboard and perform the analyses is openly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/abdelghani-maddi/osinit/blob/main/app.R>. Open science stakeholders interested in contributing are welcome to join the work on the dashboard development. Please contact the authors.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization (ID, M-A S, AM); Data curation (ID, M-A S, AM); Formal analysis (AM); Funding acquisition (M-A S, AM); Investigation (ID, M-A S, AM); Methodology (ID, M-A S, AM); Project administration (AM); Resources (ID, M-A S, AM); Software (AM); Supervision (ID, M-A S, AM); Validation (ID, M-A S, AM); Visualization (ID, M-A S, AM); Writing – original draft (ID, M-A S, AM); Writing – review & editing (ID, M-A S, AM).

Competing interests

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